

Table 2. Effect of a 10-day 12°C water treatment 10 days after sowing on the growth duration of 2 rice varieties. IRRI, 1980.

Observation	IR22553		IR20654	
	Plants (no.)	% of the population	Plants (no.)	% of the population
Delayed flowering	203	46	362	38
Same flowering duration	103	23	307	32
Early flowering	73	17	137	14
Dead	63	14	148	16
Total number tested	442		954	

crosses studied (Table 2). Some lines, however, actually headed earlier as a result of the treatment. Since the plants are still segregating, it is not possible to definitely say that the treatment caused earliness or delay in heading.

In general, the plants damaged severely

by the cold water treatment showed a greater delay in heading (Table 3). In both crosses, the difference in average flowering date between the treated plants and the control is small for plants with a score of 1 to 3. Screening for cold tolerance at the seedling stage can be

Table 3. Effect of 10-day 12°C water treatment 10 days after sowing on the yellowing of leaves of 2 rice varieties. IRRI, 1980.

Score	F ₃ plants ^a (no.)	
	IR22553	IR20654
1-3	17 (+5)	129 (+3)
Green		
5	39 (+5)	261 (+9)
Light green		
7-9	386 (+6)	564 (+8)
Yellow - dead		
Total	442	954

^aFigures inside the parentheses show the average number of days heading was delayed.

conducted during the RGA of F₃ plants without any great delay in heading of the tolerant lines. ■

Pest management and control DISEASES

Yellow wilt of rice in the lower Amazon Basin, Brazil

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The yellow wilt problem of rice was noted in a few mechanically cultivated fields of irrigated rice in the lower Amazon Basin in the second crop season of 1978. The disorder became more serious in the first and second crop seasons of 1979 on IR22 in the varzea marshland soils.

The rice plant's growth usually proceeded normally until 1 or 2 weeks before the flowering-milk stages; then the older leaves began to die rapidly and the younger leaves turned yellow brown and gradually died back from the tips. About 1 or 2 weeks before harvest, the yellow-brown leaves suddenly withered. Ripening was accelerated and at harvest the affected plants looked dehydrated, dirty, weak, and droopy; and had no green or light-yellow leaves.

Such crops had many decayed and dead roots and were usually attacked by *Helminthosporium* leaf spot, *Cercospora* leaf spot, *Pyricularia* neck blast, or *Rhizoctonia* sheath blight, or two or more of the diseases. But such attacks appeared secondary. Yields were low

because of the low photosynthetic activity of the leaves and the poor root systems. The appropriate harvest time was difficult to determine because the leaves dried and died before maturation, and the same panicles contained green as well as ripe grains. Grain quality was usually poor. In cases where the disorder occurred before flowering, plant growth was poor. A yellow-brown discoloration appeared on the tips of green leaves, and the older leaves dried and died, starting from the tips. At flowering the panicles varied in height and few leaves remained green. Leaves then withered more rapidly. Drainage for harvesting accelerated the withering. The symptoms usually occurred on plants grown in soils of low organic matter. The name *yellow wilt* was used because of the yellowing and wilting symptoms.

A combination of factors including iron toxicity, potassium deficiency, and disease incidence was suspected to cause yellow wilt. Recent studies show that the yellow wilt disorder is associated with potassium deficiency in the soil solution and low potassium content of the plants.

Increasing the supply of potassium fertilizer from the previous recommendation of 20-30 kg/ha to 70-90 kg/ha and

split application of potassium noticeably alleviated the disorder.

Three tentative remedies have been recommended:

1. submergence of the varzea marshland soils for at least 1 month before planting;
2. increase in potassium fertilizer up to 70-90 kg/ha and splitting its application; and
3. application of higher levels of potassium fertilizer, but avoidance of excessive nitrogen dressing, at about the maximum-tillering stage. ■

Experimental observations on rice sheath rot disease

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Semidwarf rice cultivars are often susceptible to sheath rot disease caused by *Acrocyndrium oryzae*, but tall cultivars are relatively resistant. Therefore research was conducted to determine if the semidwarfs' susceptibility could be altered by use of a growth substance to change the host plants' growth pattern.

Two consecutive foliar sprays of gibberellic acid (GA, 100 µg/ml) applied